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Review Article

Review On Various Analytical Approaches For The Estimation Of Rilpivirine And Its Combination In Bulk And Dosage Forms

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ABSTRACT

Rilpivirine is non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor (NNRTI) which is used for the treatment of HIV-1 infections in treatment-naive patients. It is a diarylpyrimidine derivative. The chemical name of rilpivirine is 4-{{4-({4-[(E)-2-cyanoethenyl]-2,6-dimethylphenyl}amino)-pyrimidinyl}amino}benzotrilemonohydrochloride. Present review is focused on method conditions, linearity offered, sensitivity, accuracy, precision and assay results of various analytical methods such as UV-Visible spectroscopy, HPLC and LCMS for the estimation of rilpivirine.

INTRODUCTION

Rilpivirine is non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor (NNRTI) which is used for the treatment of HIV-1 infections in treatment-naive patients. It is a diarylpyrimidine derivative. The chemical name of rilpivirine is 4-{{4-({4-[(E)-2-cyanoethenyl]-2,6-dimethylphenyl}amino)-pyrimidinyl}amino}benzotrilemonohydrochloride[3,4].

Its molecular is C₂₂H₁₈N₆.

Figure 1: Chemical Structure of Ripivirine

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Rilpivirine was developed by Tibotec, Inc. and FDA approved on May 20, 2011. The internal conformational flexibility of rilpivirine and the plasticity of its interacting binding site gives it a very high potency and reduces the chance of resistance compared to other NNRTIS. Treatment of HIV-1 infections in treatment-naïve patients

with HIV-1 RNA $\leq 100,000$ copies/mL in combination with at least 2 other antiretroviral agents. Literature survey reveals few analytical methods for the estimation of rilpivirine such as chromatographic techniques [1-18], spectrophotometric techniques [19-21], hyphenated techniques [22-25].

CHROMATOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUES 1-18

Sr. No	Mobile phase [v/v]	Flow rate & Detection wavelength	Column	Linearity [$\mu\text{g/ml}$]	Accuracy	Precision & Retention time	LOD & LOQ
1	MeCN, potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (20 mM, pH 3.3), & triethylamine 58.72: 41.23: 0.05 (v/v)	1.7 mL/min & 270 nm	Phenomenex Gemini C18 column (150 mm \times 4.6 mm i.e., 5 μm)	HPLC Emtricitabine [EMT]: 28–84 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate [TDF]: 42–126 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, & Rilpivirine [RPV]: 3.5–10.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	EMT: 99.50% TDF: 99.90% & RPV: 99%	%RSD: intraday & interday precision $\leq 2\%$ & RT: -	LOD & LOQ: EMT- 1.90, 0.43 ng/mL TDF-2.18, 0.54 ng/mL RPV-3.12, 1.78 ng/mL
2	Phosphate buffer: Acetonitrile 40:60	1.2 mL/min & 262 nm	INERTSIL column, C18 (150x4.6 ID) 5 μm	HPLC Emtricitabine: 24-56 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, Rilpivirine: 3-7 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ & Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate: 30-70 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	EMT: 100.19%, RPV: 101.30% & TDF: 99.70%	%RSD: <2% & RT: EMT: 2.523 min & RPV: 3.270 min & TDF: 6.653 min	LOD & LOQ: EMT- 22.19, 30.31 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ RPV- 3.85, 17.12 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ TDF- 17.23, 50.91 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
3	Mobile phase A: 0.02M sodium dihydrogen	1.5 ml/min & 261 nm	Inertsil ODS 3V column	RP-HPLC Emtricitabine: 8-120 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, Tenofovir disoproxil	Sol 1: EMT: 99.2 TDF: 99.2 RPV: 99.59 Sol 2:	%RSD: EMT: 0.21% TDF: 0.099% RPV: 0.34% & RT:	LOD & LOQ: EMT - 0.06, 0.14 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

	orthophosphate & Mobile phase B: Methanol and water (85:15)			fumarate: 12-180µg/ml, & Rilpivirine: 20-360µg/ml	EMT: 98.92 TDF: 100.56 RPV: 101.32 Sol 3: EMT: 100.36 TDF: 99.42 RPV: 100.95 Sol 4: EMT: 99.71 TDF: 99.32 RPV: 99.99 Sol 5: EMT: 101.07 TDF: 99.09 RPV: 99.85	EMT: 5.88 min TDF: 8.796 min RPV: 12.015 min	TDF - 0.07, 0.12 µg/ml RPV - 0.08, 0.15 µg/ml														
4	Acetonitrile, Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH2.8) & orthophosphoric acid (40:60)	1.0 ml/min & 282 nm	Develosil ODS HG-5 RP C18, 5µm, 15cmx4.6 mm	RP-HPLC Rilpivirine: 0 – 30 µg/ml	%RSD: 0.202152, 0.331525, 0.331159	Intraday <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>solution</th> <th>%RSD</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>10</td> <td>0.96</td> </tr> <tr> <td>20</td> <td>0.4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>30</td> <td>0.33</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> Interday <table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>10</td> <td>0.97</td> </tr> <tr> <td>20</td> <td>0.42</td> </tr> <tr> <td>40</td> <td>0.14</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> RT: RPV: 4.50 min	solution	%RSD	10	0.96	20	0.4	30	0.33	10	0.97	20	0.42	40	0.14	LOD & LOQ: RPV - 0.05, 0.15 µg/ml
solution	%RSD																				
10	0.96																				
20	0.4																				
30	0.33																				
10	0.97																				
20	0.42																				
40	0.14																				
5	0.1% Orthophosphoric & acetonitrile (60:40 v/v)	1.0ml/min & 262nm	Phenomenex C18 (150x4.6mm, 5µm)	RP-HPLC Dolutegravir (DTG): 10–150 µg/ml & Rilpivirine (RPV): 5–75 µg/ml	DTG: 100.22–100.45% & RPV: 100.37–100.58%	% RSD: DTG: 0.15% RPV: 0.26% RT: DTG: 4.349 min RPV: 7.730 min	LOD & LOQ: DTG - 0.01, 0.1 µg/ml RPV - 0.005, 0.05 µg/ml														
6	Mobile phase A: 0.03M dipotassium hydrogen orthophosphate	1.0 ml/min & 284 nm	Zorbax Eclipse XDB-C18, 250x4.6mm, 5 µm	RP-HPLC Rilpivirine: 100-300µg/ml	RPV: 93.50-119.10 %	%RSD: intraday & interday precision ≤2% RT: RPV: 7.19 min	LOD & LOQ: RPV - 0.05µg/ml, 0.15 µg/ml														

	sphate (pH 2.5) & dilute ortho-phosphoric acid & Mobile phase B: acetonitrile (15:85 v/v)						
7	0.1% OPA: Acetonitrile (60:40 v/v)	1.0 mL min-1 & 230 nm	INERTSIL ODS C18 (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)	RP-HPLC Dolutegravir: 50-150 µg/ml & Rilpivirine: 25-125 µg/ml	DTG:100.3 9% RPV:100.0 4%	% RSD: <2% RT: DTG: 3.410 min RPV: 4.387 min	-
8	KH ₂ PO ₄ buffer (pH 3.5) & Acetonitrile (45:55 v/v)	1mL/min & 240.0 nm	Agilent C18 column (4.6x150mm, 5µm)	RP-HPLC Dolutegravir: 12.5 -75 µg/mL & Rilpivirine: 6.25-37.5 µg/mL	DTG: 99.33% & RPV: 100.5%	%RSD: DTG - 0.9% & RPV - 0.6% RT: RPV: 2.239 min DTG: 2.899 min	LOD & LOQ: DTG - 0.2, 0.6 µg/ml RPV - 0.02, 0.06 µg/mL
9	Acetonitrile & Phosphate buffer (pH 3.5), (60:40)	1 ml/min & 282 nm	C8 Column (4.6 x 250 mm, 5 µm)	RP-HPLC Rilpivirine: 10-50 µg/mL	RPV: 99-101%	%RSD: Precision: 0.13, ID Precision: 0.004 RT: RPV: 2.755 min	LOD & LOQ: RPV - 0.005µg/ml, 0.17µg/ml
10	0.01N KH ₂ PO ₄ buffer (pH: 4.8): acetonitrile (70:30v/v)	260 nm	Agilent - C18 column (BDS) (150 X 4.6 mm, 5µm)	RP-HPLC Cabotegravir: 25-150 µg/mL & Rilpivirine: 37.5-225µg/mL	Cabotegravir: 100.25% & RPV: 99.79%	%RSD: Cabotegravir - 0.3% & RPV - 0.4% Intraday & interday precision ≤2 RT: RPV: 2.300 min Cabotegravir: 3.187 min	LOD & LOQ: Cabotegravir - 0.24, 0.74 µg/mL RPV - 1.10, 3.34 µg/mL
11	Acetonitrile: ammonium	0.8 ml/minutes &	Shim-pack C18 column	RP-HPLC Rilpivirine HCL: 5-50 µg/ml	RPV HCL: 98%-102%	%RSD: RPV HCL - 0.709% RT: RPV:	LOD & LOQ: RPV HCL - 0.104

	acetate buffer (0.05 M) (pH-3.5 equalized with glacial acetic acid), (60:40 v/v)	291 nm	(150 × 4.6 mm; 5 μ)			4.5 min	μg/ml, 0.315 μg/ml
12	0.01N ammonium acetate buffer (pH 3) & acetonitrile (65:35 v/v)	1.0 ml/min & 257 nm	Inertsil C18 (150 x 4.6 mm, 5 μm) column	RP-HPLC Cabotegravir: 10-60 μg/ml & Rilpivirine: 15-90 μg/ml	Cabotegravir: 100.71 % & RPV: 100.01 %	%RSD: < 2% RT: Cabotegravir: 2.250 min RPV: 2.823 min	LOD & LOQ: Cabotegravir - 0.13 μg/ml, 0.38 μg/ml RPV - 0.16 μg/ml, 0.48 μg/ml
13	0.01N Potassium dihydrogen phosphate: Acetonitrile (60:40)	1.0 ml/min & 257 nm	Kromasil C18 150 x 4.6 mm, 5μ	RP-HPLC Cabotegravir: 18.75-112.5μg/ml Rilpivirine: 12.5- 75μg/ml	RPV: 100.13% & Cabotegravir: 100.43%	%RSD: RPV: 0.5% & Cabotegravir: 1.4% RT: RPV: 2.257 min Cabotegravir: 2.642 min	LOD & LOQ: RPV - 0.18 μg/ml, 0.54 μg/ml Cabotegravir - 0.15 μg/ml, 0.46 μg/ml
14	Mobile phase: phosphate buffer: acetonitrile (60:40% v/v), (pH 6.8)	1.0ml/min & 272nm	Ymc C18 short column	RP-HPLC Rilpivirine: 1-10μg/ml	RPV: 0.6397%	%RSD: RPV: 0.6845 RT: RPV: 3.137 min	LOD & LOQ: RPV - 0.0427μg/ml, 0.724 μg/ml
15	Chloroform: ethyl acetate: methanol: glacial acetic acid (5:2:1:0.	272 nm	Aluminium plates: silica gel 60 F254	HPTLC Emtricitabine: 600-2400 ng band ⁻¹ Rilpivirine: 50-300 ng bands ⁻¹ Tenofovir disoproxil	EMT: 100.01% RPV: 100.32% TDF: 100.14%	%RSD: intraday and interday precision% (<2%) EMT: 99.91% RPV: 98.72% TDF: 99.34%	LOD & LOQ: EMT – 5.0164, 15.2012 ng/band RPV -

	1 v/v/v/v)			fumarate: 600- 3600 ng band ⁻¹		RT: -	4.25, 12.8790 ng/band TFV – 5.5063, 16.6890 ng/band
16	35% of 0.1M tri ethyl amine buffer & 65% Acetonit rile	0.3 ml/min & 260 mμ	Thermosil Octa Decyl Column (4.6 x 50mm, 1.7 mm)	RP-UPLC- PDA –	Mean recovery: 100.48%	%RSD: <2 RT: Emtricitabine: 0.965 min, Tenofovir Alafenamide: 1.528 min, RPV: 2.186 min	LOD & LOQ: 3.00 μg/ml, 9.98 μg/ml
17	0.1% ortho phospho ric acid & acetonitr ile (55:45% v/v)	1 mL/min & 260 nm	SB C8 column (100 x 3 mm, 1.8 mm)	RP-UPLC Dolutegravir: 12.5 – 75.0 μg/mL Rilpivirine: 6.25 – 37.5 μg/mL	% Recovery: DOL: 99.04 - 99.79% RIL: 99.20 - 99.92%	%RSD: <2.0 RT: Dolutegravir: 1.25 min RPV: 1.69 min	LOD & LOQ: DOL: 0.281 & 0.852 μg/ml RIL: 0.281 & 0.152 μg/ml
18	methano l: water: 0.1% ortho phospho ric acid (80:10:1 0 v/v/v)	1.5ml/mi n & 230nm	Zodiac C18 (250x4.6m m, 5μm in particle size)	LC Rilpivirine:4- 10 μg/ml	Mean recovery: 98.3 to 100.1%	%RSD: <1.0% Intraday: 0.8 - 1.08 Interday: 0.9 - 1.27 RT: RPV: 3.83 min	LOD & LOQ: 0.06 μg/ml, 0.2μg/ml
19	HPTLC: ethyl acetate: methano l: chlorofo rm (8.0:1.0: 1.0%v/v/ v)	254nm	–	HPTLC Rilpivirine:5- 30 μg/spot	%RSD: 0.8692%	%RSD: 0.3044 RT: -	LOD & LOQ: 0.317 μg/ml, 0.513 μg/ml

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC TECHNIQUES19-21

S.NO	Solvents	Linearity [μg/ml]	λmax (nm)	Comment
20	Methanol	UV	EMT: 240.8nm	UV region

		Emtricitabine: 4–12 µg/ml, Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate: 6–18 µg/ml, Ralpivirine HCl: 0.5–1.5 µg/ml	TDF: 257.6nm RPV: 305.6nm	
21	Acetonitrile: Water (50:50)	UV 4-20µg/ml	304nm	UV region
22	Methanol	UV 2-8µg/ml	282nm	UV region

HYPHENATED TECHNIQUES22-25

Sr. NO	Mobile phase (v/v)	Flow rate (ml/min)	Column	Linearity & Retention Time
23	5 mM Ammonium acetate, 20.0% & Acetonitrile, 80% (20:80% v/v)	0.70 ml/min	Zorbax 5 µ, C18, 100×4.60 mm	LC-MS-MS Tenofovir: 5.000 - 600.00 ng/mL Ralpivirine: 1.000-203.00 ng/mL RT: Tenofovir: 0.85 min RPV: 2.80 min
24	Acetonitrile & 0.1% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid in water (81:19, v/v)	0.3 mL/min	Apex Scientific Inertsil ODS-3 column (4.6 mm × 250 mm, 5 µm particle size)	HPLC-MS Ralpivirine: 0-150 ng/ml Cabotegravir: 0-25000 ng/ml RT: RPV: 6.846 min Cabotegravir: 9.835 min
25	55% of water (0.05% formic acid, v/v) and 45% of methanol (0.05% formic acid, v/v)	0.5mL/min	Kinetex phehyl-hexyl column	HPLC-MS-MS Darunavir (DRV): 60 to 15000 ng/mL Dolutegravir (DTG) & Elvitegravir (ELV): 20 to 5000 ng/mL

				Raltegravir (RAL), Raltegravir- β -D-glucuronide (RAL-GLU), Ritonavir (RTV) and Rilpivirine (RPV): 10 to 2500 ng/mL RT: RAL-GLU: 2.8 min, RPV: 4.0 min, RAL: 5.3 min, DRV: 6.1min, DTG: 6.7 min, ELV: 9.1 min, RTV: 9.4 min
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CONCLUSION:

Upon extensive literature survey, it was found that quite a good spectrophotometric, chromatographic as well as hyphenated techniques were reported for the quantification of Rilpivirine. Therefore, this study may help researchers in developing a simple, precise and robust method for the quantification of rilpivirine and its combinations.

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